

Amortised simulation-based inference in diffusion MRI using artificial neural networks

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Introduction

Given the high data dimensionality coming with modern diffusion MRI (dMRI) protocols (e.g., [1]), the potentially large space of parameters [2] and/or the lack of tractable likelihoods in some cases, traditional inference for microstructure models can be slow, computationally demanding or, directly, unusable. We present a Simulation-Based Inference (SBI) framework alternative [3] applied to voxel-wise microstructural modelling for dMRI data [4]. SBI allows to combine learning of latent features of importance from networks (e.g., Deep Nets), the interpretability of mechanistic models (e.g., multi-compartment models) and Bayesian principles (uncertainty mapping). We evaluate SBI against a classical inference framework, based on conventional random-walk Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo (MCMC) [5].

Methods

To estimate the posterior distribution of the model parameters θ given data x , $P(\theta|x) \sim P(x|\theta)P(\theta)$, classical methods, such as MCMC, are usually iterative and require explicit likelihood calculations $P(x|\theta)$. SBI recasts this as a *density estimation* problem instead, where a parametric model Q_ϕ that takes as inputs pairs of datapoints (u, v) returns a conditional probability density $Q_\phi(u|v)$ that is an approximation to the true conditional density $P(u|v)$. The approximator Q_ϕ can be an artificial neural networks (ANN) [6] (Fig.1A) that learns a mapping between the posterior distribution of model parameters and observations, as long as forward predictions $f_x(\theta)$ (i.e. simulations) can be obtained for training [3]. This enables amortised inference for new data, i.e. inference with a single pass to the network, without model inversion.

To obtain distributions rather than point estimates, we embedded a conditional density estimator into the ANN, in the form of Normalizing Flows [7,8]. We built SBI for the Ball&Stick model as an exemplar for $f_x(\theta)$ to create a simulated training dataset $\{\theta_N, x_N\}$ (1M simulated sets for training). We evaluated performance against a random-walk Metropolis-Hastings MCMC on both synthetic and real data. We generated noisy realisations of single-shell data (64 directions, $b=1000 \text{ s/mm}^2$), while varying volume fraction, diffusivity and fibre orientation and compared estimates to ground truth. We also used in-vivo brain dMRI data ($2 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ voxels, 64 directions, $b=1000 \text{ s/mm}^2$). Using the estimated orientations, we also performed probabilistic tractography using XTRACT [9].

Results

Both MCMC and SBI provided a similar signal reconstruction (exemplar cases in Fig.1B) and low estimation errors in synthetic examples ($<5\%$ for volume fraction and, $<10^\circ$ for fibre orientation and for different SNR levels, see Fig.1C). Regarding precision, the standard deviation of the posterior distributions are in the order of 2-5% of the estimated value for both SBI and MCMC for average SNR

levels, apart from diffusivity where SBI returns a wider posterior than MCMC (Fig.1B). In in-vivo data, the SBI estimates are compared directly to the MCMC outputs. There is a high level of agreement in mean estimates between both approaches (Fig.2A), although SBI estimates smaller uncertainty in fibre orientation than MCMC (i.e. overconfidence), particularly in crossing regions where the single stick model is not adequate. Nevertheless, the tract bundles obtained by running probabilistic tractography show a high correlation ($r=0.74$ on average) with those obtained using MCMC.

In terms of computational performance, the ANN training required 113 minutes and SBI whole-brain inference took 20 minutes on a single CPU core, while the equivalent single-core time for the MCMC would >100 hours. This reflects a speed-up of 2-3 orders of magnitude in model inference once the network is trained.

Conclusion

SBI approaches provide higher flexibility and major advantages in terms of computational efficiency with respect to classical approaches, such as the MCMC, while keeping the accuracy of estimation.

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A)

B)

C)

D)

Fig.1. A) SBI scheme implementation: Using the priors $P(\theta)$ we can produce parameter proposals θ_i , then simulate the correspondent dMRI dataset x_i using the model $f(\theta)$ and use those to learn an approximated posterior density $Q_\phi(\hat{\theta}_i|x_i)$. The learnt posterior density $Q_\phi(\hat{\theta}_i|x_i)$ is amortised, i.e., when trained correctly, it can be used to infer the posterior density of parameters for any new observations. **B)** Exemplar reconstructed signals (randomly-chosen synthetic data realisations) using the estimates given by MCMC (orange) and SBI (blue) compared to the ground-truth values (black dashed line). **C)** Accuracy (top) and precision (bottom) of obtained MCMC and SBI estimates for different synthetic noisy realisations, for the volume fraction and the fibre orientation. For accuracy, the mean of the posterior samples is compared to ground truth values, while the variance of the posterior samples is used as precision. **D)** Scatter plots of MCMC and SBI mean f_1 estimates compared to the ground-truth for low and high SNR levels.

